

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF TITRATIONS

Indicator	Reductant (s)	Acidity range, M
LBBF	Fe(II), Sb(III) and hydroquinone	1.0–3.0
	As(III) ^α	1.0–2.0
	U(IV), Mo(V) and oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	V(IV)	0.2–0.4+6.0–8.0 M acetic acid.
SBSG	Fe(II) and hydroquinone	1.0–2.0
	Sb(III), As(III) ^α and Mo(V)	1.5–3.0
	Oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	U(IV) and V(IV)	Titration is not satisfactory
BCB ^β	Sb(III), As(III) ^α and hydroquinone	1.0–2.0
	U(IV) and oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	Mo(V)	2.0–4.0
	V(IV)	0.2–0.4+6.0–8.0 M acetic acid.
ABS ^φ	Fe(II) and hydroquinone	1.0–2.0
	As(III) ^α	1.5–3.0
	Oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	Sb(III), U(IV), V(IV) and Mo(V)	Titration is not possible.
RB ^φ	Fe(II)	1.0–2.0
	Sb(III)	1.5–3.0
	Oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	As(III) ^α , U(IV), V(IV), Mo(V), and hydroquinone	Titration is not possible.

^α 5–8 drops of 0.25% osmic acid or 0.5 ml of 0.005 M ferron is used as catalyst.

^β Sriramam^{*} has reported BCB as indicator in the Fe(II)-cerate (IV) titration.

^φ The indicator should be added at about 0.5–1.0 ml before the end point.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to E.I. du Pont de Nemours & Company, Wilmington, Delaware, U.S.A., for a gift of SBSG, and to the U.G.C. for the award of a Teacher Fellowship to K.R.K.M. and financial assistance to N.V.R.

References

1. N. V. RAO, A. B. AVADHANULU and K. SRIKRISHNA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 283.
2. N. V. RAO and A. B. AVADHANULU, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1977, 283, 301.
3. A. B. AVADHANULU, Ph.D. thesis, Andhra University, Waltair, 1977, p 118.
4. K. SRIRAMAM, *Tal. nta.*, 1975, 22, 78.
5. N. V. RAO and K. M. M. KRISHNA PRASAD, *Curr. Sci.*, 1978, 47, 50.
6. K. M. M. KRISHNA PRASAD, Ph.D. thesis, Andhra University, Waltair, 1978, p. 164.

A Semiempirical Relation for the Interaction Moment

$\Delta\mu$ in H-Bonded Complexes

M. MEYYAPPAN and K. EK-A NARENDARAN

Department of Physics, Rajah Serfoji Government College, Thanjavur-5, 613 005.

Manuscript received 4 July 1978; revised 19 October 1978; accepted 23 March 1979.

IN H-bonding, in addition to major electrostatic interaction, delocalization, dispersion and repulsive interactions also play an appreciable role¹. However the

stronger H-bonds with large interaction moment $\Delta\mu$ along the A-H...B axis ($\mu_{complex} = \mu_{AH} - \mu_B$) in the cases of complexes of picric and hydrobromic acid with trialkylamines can be explained only on the basis of proton transfer effect²⁻⁴. Ratajczak et al.,^{5,6} made

an attempt to understand the influence of $\Delta\mu$ on the strength and polarity of hydrogen bonds by considering both inductive and tautomeric effects and showed that the polarity of H-bonds mainly depends on the acidity of A-H, the p_a value of the acidic component. They also found that the enhancement of dipole moment in triethylamine-phenols complex³ in nonpolar solvents changes continuously within a wide range from 0.30 to

about 10.00 D. To account such high polarity ($\Delta\mu > 3.0$ D) they suggested the possibility of proton transfer complexes with an equilibrium of type

and the interaction moments in the range 3-10 D may be due to the coexistence of H-bonded and proton transfer complexes. The existing proton transfer equilibrium leads to the linear relationship between $\Delta\mu$ and

the mole fraction of proton transfer species. i.e., $\Delta\mu = A+Bx$, where A is the dipole moment of non-proton transfer complexes and B, the dipole moment of ion-

pairs. $\Delta\mu$, in complexes with a fixed electron donating and α varying electron accepting groups, in general, rises with an increase in acidity of A-H (fall in p_a)

NOTES

and this dependence of the polarity of the H-bond on pK_a has been confirmed by many authors⁶⁻⁷.

From the detailed analysis of acid-base complexes of a set of different proton donors (alcohols, phenols and benzoic acids) with a given proton acceptor (triethylamine^{2,6,7}, tributylamine^{2,6} and pyridine^{2,7,8}) it is observed that the partial proton transfer species show a regular change in the strength of hydrogen bond formed in them with an increase in acidity of proton donor.

Thus the hydrogen bond moment $\Delta\mu$ may be expressed by the following general relation

$$\Delta\mu = a + b pK_a + \Delta$$

where Δ is a correction factor, the exact value of which depends upon the influence of the external conditions imposed by the molecules involved and by the surrounding molecules on the H-bonding interaction. It includes the polarity of the solvent and the specific solvation of the H-bonded complexes. The complexes due to partial proton transfer are more stable than true ion-pairs⁹ and in such complexes Δ is more or less a constant for a given system of acid-base complexes. As a result of which the proton transfer species do not deviate from the linear relationship between the acidity

and $\Delta\mu$. For both the weak and strong H-bonds Δ' significantly deviates from its constant value Δ . ($\Delta' - \Delta$) is positive in weak H-bonded complexes and may be due to the existence of resonance structure of type $A^- \dots H - B^+$ and it is negative in strong H-bonded complexes, where the dipole-dipole interaction of the ion-pairs, which is inversely proportional to the cube of the distance between the dipoles¹⁰ is quite appreciable.

The proton transfer effect is more predominate within a domain of pK_a values (roughly 5 to 8) bound by weak and strong acids. With available literature

values⁹ of $\Delta\mu$ for 1:1 proton transfer complexes of various triethylamine-phenols systems, the best approximate values for the constants a and b are determined.

The simple linear relation between $\Delta\mu$ and pK_a of the acid component of the given series of triethylamine-phenols is

$$\Delta\mu = 16.65 - 1.992 pK_a$$

This relation is used to estimate $\Delta\mu$ of triethylamine-phenols complexes and the values are given in Table 1.

The proposed relation explains the linear dependence of dipole moment on the molar fraction of proton transfer species and holds good for H-bonds in triethylamine-phenols complexes within a domain of H-bonding

strength ($\Delta\mu = 2$ to $8D$). Beyond this domain, the contribution due to the interaction of solvent molecules with H-bonded complexes and due to the dipole-dipole interaction is quite appreciable^{11,12}. Thus the appreciable deviation in simple H-bonded complexes between triethylamine and weaker phenols such as *p*-cresol, phenol and in ion-pair formation in the case of strong acids such as picric and hydrobromic acids may be due to the changes in Δ factor. The H-bond interaction moment in triethylamine-picric acid³ ($\mu_{A-H \dots B} = 11.7 D$ and $pK_a = 0.42$) is $9.4 D$. It gives a rough estimation of the maximum value of ($\Delta' - \Delta$) and is equal to

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $\Delta\mu$ FOR TRIETHYLAMINE-PHENOLS COMPLEXES

phenol derivative	μ^* complex	$\Delta\mu$	$\Delta\mu$ present work	pK_a	Δ -factor
<i>m</i> -nitrophenol	5.32	1.1	0.05	8.35	Δ' ($\Delta' - \Delta$) is positive.
<i>p</i> -cyanophenol	6.83	1.7	1.67	7.52	
<i>p</i> -nitrophenol	7.26	2.0	2.41	7.15	$\Delta = \text{constant}$
3,5-dinitrophenol	7.86	3.3	3.30	6.70	
2,4,6-trichlorophenol	7.05	4.7	4.70	6.00	
2,5-dinitrophenol	9.08	6.8	6.25	5.22	Δ'
2,4-dinitrophenol	11.26	7.9	8.54	4.07	
2,6-dichloro-4-nitrophenol	11.96	8.8	9.27	3.68	

* Reference 3.

μ values are expressed in Debye unit.

-6.4D. The extrapolation of linear relationship to wake
 $\rightarrow$
 phenols shows that $\Delta\mu=0$ as $p_k \rightarrow 7.3$. It estimates that the maximum value of $(\Delta' - \Delta)$ due to conjugation effect in weak H-bonded complexes i.e., the delocalization of the π -electrons through a hydrogen bond^{1a} is 2.00 D. The correction factor Δ , in fact measures the changes in the nature of polarity of the structure. Thus the possible conformers of molecules involved in complexes may be one of the factors to which Δ may depend upon. However the actual mechanism of its variation is still questionable.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere gratitude to Prof. K. Ramasamy, Annamalai University, for his helpful discussions.

References

1. C. A. COULSON., Hydrogen bonding, Hadzi Ed., Pergamon Press, London, 1959, p. 339.
2. J. W. SMITH., *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1964, 61, 125.
3. H. RATAJCZAK and L. SOB CZYK, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, 50, 556.
4. H. RATAJCZAK and L. SOB CZYK, *Bull. Acad. Pol. Sci.*, 1970, 18, 93.
5. L. SOB CZYK and J. K. SYRKIN, *Roczn. Chem.*, 1956, 30, 881, 893; 1957, 31, 197, 204, 1245.
6. K. BAUGE and J. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, A, 616.
7. H. RATAJCZAK and L. SOB CZYK, *Zh. Strukt. Chim.*, 1965, 6, 262.
8. M. DAVIES and L. SOB CZYK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 3000.
9. S. N. VINOGRADOV and R. H. LINNELL, Hydrogen bonding, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, New York, 1971, p. 168.
10. J. M. LEHN and G. OURISSON, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1963, 1113.
11. J. R. HULETT, J. A. PEGG and L. E. SUTTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3901.
12. H. TSUBOMURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1958, 31, 435.
13. R. M. SCOTT and S. N. VINOGRADOV, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 1890.

Synthesis of Naphtho α - and γ -Pyrone Derivatives from 1,4-Dihydroxy Naphthalene

(Miss.) J. H. PARDANANI, Y. G. GAEKWAD
 and
 SURESH SETHNA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002.

Manuscript received 2 January 1979, accepted 27 April 1979

IN continuation of previous work¹ we have now studied the synthesis of α - and γ -pyrone derivatives from 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene.

1,4-Dihydroxy naphthalene on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of conc. sulphuric

acid gave 4-hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone (I, R=H) (m.p. 282°), earlier prepared by Desai and Sethna² by persulphate oxidation of naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone. Buu Hoi and Lavit³ who carried out this condensation in alcoholic solution using hydrogen chloride gas as the condensing agent obtained a product m. p. 206° to which they assigned the above structure. In order to ascertain the nature of this product we repeated Buu Hoi's work and obtained the product m.p. 206°. Its NMR spectrum showed the absence of a free hydroxyl group, but the presence of a 4-ethoxy group. On de-ethylation with anhydrous aluminium chloride it gave the product m.p. 282°, which when subjected to the action of hydrogen chloride in presence of alcohol gave back the product m.p. 206°. Buu Hoi's product is therefore 4-ethoxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone (I, R=C₂H₅).

The γ -pyrone derivative was obtained from 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene by refluxing it with ethyl acetoacetate in boiling diphenyl ether. It was different from the α -pyrone (I, R=H) and gave on alkaline hydrolysis 1,4-dihydroxy-2-acetyl naphthalene. It has been assigned 4-hydroxy-2'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') γ -pyrone (II) structure. It is known that such a condensation gives γ -pyrone derivatives⁴.

Experimental

4-Hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone : A mixture of 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene (2 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (4 ml.) and conc. sulphuric acid (8 ml.) was kept overnight. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice was soluble in alkali. It was crystallised from acetic acid. M.P. 282°. Yield 0.6 g. Desai and Sethna² reported m.p. 285°. IR (nujol) cm^{-1} : 3170 (OH), 1675 (CO).

The acetyl derivative : The above product (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and sodium acetate (1.5 g.) for 1.1/2 hr. and the product obtained crystallised from ethyl acetate in fine needles m.p. 183°. (Found : C, 71.37; H, 4.00. C₁₆H₁₂O₄ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.47%).

4-Ethoxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone : A cooled solution of 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene (2 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (4 ml.) in ethanol (25 ml.) was saturated with hydrogen chloride gas. The reaction